

The Total House During and After Coronavirus: The Architecture of Virtual Place and More

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Abstract

We are aware that the phenomenon we are currently experiencing as a result of the Coronavirus pandemic is producing radical implications in terms of environmental transformations, changes in the relationship between man and nature and social relationships. These major questions are leading us once again to think "big" and to formulate new theories, which inevitably involve all our spheres of knowledge. One of the topics that will continue to be linked to this long, exhausting struggle against Covid-19 is that of social distancing. This is the expression around which the phase or phases revolve, which have confined all, or nearly all of us within our own four walls.

*Social distancing is an expression, which has been discussed in depth, and various sociological, anthropological and psychological theories have been compared since the nineteen thirties. According to Vincenzo Cesareo the concept of social distancing before Covid-19 was understood as "the relational closure of an individual towards others, who are perceived and recognised as different depending on the social categories to which they can be traced. It is the result of the dynamic interlacing of factors from different dimensions in space: physical, symbolic and geometric." A pandemic wipes out social and cultural categories and extends the principle of Physical geometric distancing to all of humanity without distinction. We are speaking of a space which expands in terms of linear metres and which, on the contrary, shrinks to within a telematic, virtual dimension. With Covid-19 we now know what it means to work, read. Communicate, take part in events, conferences, exhibitions, travel and carry out research within a single, infinite, fluid space. In terms of architecture and town planning, the virtual space corresponds to an annulment of the traditional, physical distances between living, work and recreation, which for Le Corbusier represented the functional and spatial categories established in the Athens Charter and which were part of the principles and rules to construct the future city. Similarly, virtual communication has seen the continual decrease in distance between public and private space, and the most appropriate place to contain different functions and spatial requirements is actually the home. First and foremost, we have been able to ascertain that the house has the potential to transform into a multi-functional space, a place where we live, work, carry out research, communicate with the world, into a place of recreation and entertainment, in a public, yet at the same time private area and, therefore, a **total space**, in which everything can be automated and where everything can be perfect: our bodies, objects and furnishings. Perhaps after the pandemic, our cities will consist of a group of total houses where cars will transform into perfect chauffeurs, in which materials, such as metamaterials or 3D graphene will be able to make us invisible or make us live in transparent structures made of very fine but, at the same time, extremely resistant membranes. Perhaps we will not need to design and construct public places, merely because they will be of no use, and perhaps cities of the future will only have underground department stores with long travelators and service lifts. The goods purchased will be sent directly to our homes via the lifts*

Keyword: *Virtual place, social distancing, future house, total space, virtual dimension*

Full text

We are aware that the phenomenon we are currently experiencing as a result of the Coronavirus pandemic is producing radical implications in terms of environmental transformations, changes in the relationship between man and nature and social relationships. These major questions are leading us once again to think "big" and to formulate new theories, which inevitably involve all our spheres of knowledge.

From an architectural point of view, the state of emergency in which we find ourselves leads us to imagine the future, as we have done during past disasters, and to reconsider the concept of utopia. In this case, however, it is not merely a science-fiction and visionariness but, as we've been taught by Richard Buckminster Fuller, as a true prediction of future¹. To be more precise, as we will see, residential architecture represents the cornerstone of research and as we move from physical to virtual communication,

it will certainly become the most suitable place for future experiments. The importance of residential construction emerges most clearly when the concept of automation is integrated with that of the smart city as part of a new concept of intelligent architecture. By exploiting the most advanced technologies currently in use in construction, IT and plant engineering, the home actually appears to have the potential to transform into a highly flexible, functional space, not only from a plant engineering and computer technology viewpoint but, as we have said before, also mainly from a distributive, constructive and aesthetic point of view. We will be specifically analysing the problem from an interdisciplinary perspective to better introduce the aforementioned architectural principles.

Covid19 and the Social Distancing

One of the topics that will continue to be linked to this long, exhausting struggle against Covid-19 is that of *social distancing*. This is the expression around which the phase or phases revolve, which have confined all, or nearly all of us within our own four walls.

Social distancing² is an expression, which has been discussed in depth, and various sociological, anthropological and psychological theories have been compared since the nineteen thirties. According to Vincenzo Cesario³ the concept of social distancing before Covid-19 was understood as "the relational closure of an individual towards others, who are perceived and recognised as different depending on the social categories to which they can be traced. It is the result of the dynamic interlacing of factors from different dimensions in space: physical, symbolic and geometric." A pandemic wipes out social and cultural categories and extends the principle of *Physical geometric distancing* to all of humanity without distinction. We are speaking of a space which expands in terms of linear metres and which, on the contrary, shrinks to within a telematic, virtual dimension.⁴

As we learn from Fabio Introini⁵ in one of his articles entitled *La distanza sociale. Dimensioni teoriche e attualità di un concetto classico*: "It has been highlighted several times that contemporary society is defined by the semantics of space. Globalisation: this is actually a term which magnifies the geometric aspects at the expense of time. This space, in turn, appears to lose every connotation and true strength by amalgamating with the smooth, zero gravity surface of telematic or cyber space, or with the space of the flows within which, whatever we want to call it, territorial feelings of belonging appear to lose all importance, while social processes are being remodelled.⁶" New information and communication technologies not only actually abolish the time and need to move physically, but also enable social spatiality to even out and thus conform to emergency health prerogatives⁷. An increasingly interconnected world is, in fact, a world in which relationships between individuals appear capable of dipping into total purity as new, virtual communications methods appear to balance out the old, currently obsolete, social differences as they remodel. To speak of social distancing in the current, historic and cultural context means supporting and encouraging the passage from a physical, spatial dimension to the fluid, infinite dimension of virtual space. Physical and social spaces are not disintegrating. However, they are losing their traditional level footing while supplementing each other in other types of relations. In view of the current situation, an analysis of the types and processes of social distancing in contemporary society involves a journey through the most complex, chaotic dynamics running through them.

It is worth reflecting on this viewpoint simply because the new meaning of social distancing, understood as the physical distance between individuals corresponding to a virtual closeness, becomes the salient aspect of the problem. The catastrophe generated by Covid-19 has actually *accelerated the globalisation of virtual intelligence*, by increasing the awareness of a profound transition and of a cultural revolution, which humanity has been experiencing for some time now, equal only to the rise of the Industrial Era. In other words, we are re-locating from one century to another, from one ideological period of time to a post-ideological time, where ancient certainties find it hard to resist and where unexpected events following one after the other leave the individual facing a reality « of unrest and leaving the 20th century to enter the 21st century with certain categories of ideas»⁸. Regardless of the pandemic, the historic cycle linked to modernity and post-modernity has finally come to a close, to open up new paths towards virtual communication and technological innovations. However, until the arrival of Covid-19, this process was unnoticeable, as it still belonged to a symbolic, order and to a purely immaterial, veiled setting which was, therefore, hard to decode.

The trauma currently felt across the globe has violently flung mankind into a near future, and transformed what had been a topic for a few experts in the field into a mass phenomenon.

Traumatic Events and Momentous Shifts

Natural, criminal or health disasters have always been driving force behind changing and transitional moments in ways of thinking and living; often accompanied by effects the individual finds that disorientating and destabilising. Periods, as Serge Latouche claims, which: "could also be opportunities of reawakening. Catastrophes and crises are sources of suffering, but also moments to raise awareness, to rekindle debate, to refuse and revolt"⁹.

As already mentioned, the response by architecture falls, as has always happened, in the concept of *utopia*, understood not as visionary imagination,¹⁰ but rather as a search to identify an ideal society, which corresponds to the design of an ideal place. Utopia also, and above all, understood as a *prediction* of an immediate future,¹¹ with the intention of offering concrete answers. All Buckminster Fuller's research¹² centered on utopia in reality was directed to the benefit of humanity. His works, considered utopian, actually aimed to offer concrete solutions for the cultural and political transformations following on from the Second World War throughout the world. In 1967, Tetrahedral City¹³ was a prefabricated, floating city, designed down to the last detail for a million inhabitants. The only reason it was never built was because the customer, a wealthy Japanese entrepreneur, died a few years before construction began. Fuller imagined a society seen as an aggregation of individuals, educated individually on ecology and the self-management of natural resources. A complex structure, far from the traditional concept of society, seen as a completed entity.

It is an unusual way of responding to the unstoppable phenomenon of consumerism. Once we become aware of the fact that the relationship between man and nature can be remodelled in a «convivial dimension», in compliance with the laws of entropy, we can work to produce: "less material consumption and more inner riches, less «well being» and more «good living¹⁴»".

The utopian cities, designed from the first half of the 19th century, represent the society of production and aim above all at economic and technological progress. The second revolution¹⁵ with its innumerable reforms and discoveries produced original social models, which corresponded to new urban systems. Robert Owen's 1817 Town Planning Report¹⁶, Fourier's Falansterio, Étienne Cabet's Icaria of 1848, James Buckingham's Victoria of 1849¹⁷, Godin's Familisterio in 1859, W. H. Lever's Industrial Colony in Port Sunlight in 1887, the Linear City of Soria y Mata of 1882 and Ebenezer Howard's Garden City 1889, all aimed to provide a radical alternative to the traditional, compact development model of the city around an original nucleus. Importance was given to mechanised transport infrastructures (first and foremost the railway), which became the matrices for the urban settlement. Godin's Familistère, one of the few utopian projects to be constructed, stands close to a factory and was an alternative solution to the difficult conditions of the urban working class, employed in the new manufacturing activities¹⁸. In 1914, Tony Garnier designed the Industrial City from the first to the last building, concentrating mainly on the technical aspects. There were major innovations, such as the use of starkly adorned, reinforced concrete for all the buildings: «with absolutely no extravagance unless dictated by precise, generally acknowledged requirements»¹⁹.

After traumatic events, the utopian architects also created works as a warning, as an exhortation to raise awareness of a reality, which was developing into a catastrophe and required new project hypotheses, using the tools of science, technology, art and philosophy. Examples such as the feverish solutions of Archigram on the one hand,²⁰ and Richard Buckminster Fuller's Dome over Manhattan on the other, were concrete answers to consumerism and air pollution, in the same way as Superstudio's Spaceship City and Archizoom's No-Stop City responded to the problem of unconditional urbanisation and the depersonalisation of the individual. In the 50s, the Smithsons or the Independent Group²¹ also saw their work as a response to the Second World War by creating a plain, simple, true, and essential style of architecture based on new ethics of project design.

Nowadays, social uniformity and the mindful awareness of reality, highlighted by the phrase "we'll manage together" or "united in the fight against coronavirus" which the coronavirus has produced, together with the social homogeneity typical of the virtual space, appear to coincide with the democratic idea of equality,

which are the foundation of past utopian visions. We have been violently catapulted into an immediate future and into a new utopian dimension which, this time, requires urgent answers of designs and new theories in all fields of knowledge. " It is above all in periods of crisis like these that man goes in search of new utopias, places without place, a different, spaceless and timeless (atemporal and aspatial) elsewhere to what we are experiencing"²², in which to be able to imagine life in a better world.

To Imagine the Future, an Unprecedented Opportunity

So if we launch into the immediate future, as architects we may wonder: what will our new, everyday, written or spoken words be and what will things be like in the near future? Should we imagine life follow in the footsteps of the guidelines of new utopia²³? And what will the physical or virtual space in which we live be like?

Recent claims by Stefano Boeri and Massimiliano Fuksas, which envisage the rediscovery of villages and very tiny towns as a response to the pandemic, should be considered pleonastic and hardly suitable, as they are not in line with the reality we are currently experiencing. Furthermore, the ideal of the little town risks being an illusion, since it was actually the small towns in Lombardy that were the initial hotbeds of the virus, since social interaction there is historically greater than in the cities, where physical proximity is not always social interaction.

A Possible Answer from Virtual Communication

A possible answer in our sector could be found in *virtual communication*. We are unequivocally aware that, in the era of the Internet, the meaning of our world increasingly requires the use of tools, platforms and infrastructures linked to the Internet. This phenomenon does actually lead to a transformation of social relationships into virtual entities, but does not drag the individual towards *isolation*.

Above all, when there is a pandemic, the term *social distancing* implies, as mentioned previously, a physical distance which, not by chance, is expressed in metres. However, it also implies a desire to remain united, to be part of a group, of a "community" and to work on social solidarity especially as part of a network.

According to Patricia Wallace²⁴, it is easier to see phenomena of group polarisation via the network to form *echo chambers*, virtual places in which people can interact. It is worth highlighting once again that the network is not wiping out relationships between people. On the contrary, it is merely modifying considerably the ways in which emotional relations between individuals begin and change with the Internet. Chat lines and social networks enable people to get to know one another from a distance according to their interests and passions: all this revolutionises how we socialise. This tends to become less concrete in the form of virtual bonds.²⁵

Virtual relationships differ greatly from real relationships, because they can be based on anonymity or on the partial revelation of one's identity, and also because they lack the gestures and visual and body descriptions of a two-person relationship. Perhaps we are increasingly moving towards a society based on abstract components of relationships. However, the Internet is unquestionably proving to be a powerful means of bringing people together. The characteristics of socialisation are changing. Nevertheless, as we have already mentioned, the advantages in terms of overcoming socio-cultural barriers and of localising the protagonists of the socialisation process are on the increase²⁶.

The Space between Face-To-Face and Virtual

As we also have the chance to choose between the two options of *face-to-face* and *virtual*, virtual communication could undoubtedly be a valid alternative to physical communication. The virtual place is not, therefore, a non place. Instead, it is the new place, within which we can potentially be everywhere with everyone and where time is reduced enormously. With Covid-19 we now know what it means to work, read. Communicate, take part in events, conferences, exhibitions, travel and carry out research within a single, infinite, fluid space.

If we apply this apparently trivial statement to architecture, we can begin to reconsider the term of relational space, as it is really virtual space corresponds to an annulment of the traditional, physical distances between *living, work and recreation*, which for Le Corbusier represented the functional and spatial categories

established in the Athens Charter²⁷ and which were part of the principles and rules to construct the future city. Similarly, virtual communication has seen the continual decrease in distance between public and private space, and the most appropriate place to contain different functions and spatial requirements is actually the *home*.

Home architecture will, therefore, actually need to change its distributive, functional, constructional and structural features. Thus we start from the residential architecture.

It is worth remembering in addition that the home is, and has been from the very start conceived as man's best refuge. When man crossed over from being hunter to farmer, he felt the need to find a refuge: in caves, in temporary shelters and by creating structures of straw and hay. In recent years, momentous phenomena have always seen the topic of the single family residence as a subject for research and experiments by numerous maestri of architecture. Ville Savoye, Villa Mairea, the Glass House, Falling Water, Casa Schröder, Casa Moller, Sudgen House, all bear witness to this and have become true theoretical manifestos of avant-garde architecture.

The Total House: A New Utopia as a *Prediction* of an Immediate Future

If all the above is true, as it is true to say that the virtual place is discovered within the home, and the latter is, in turn, considered to be the best place for experimenting, we wonder: how will our home space change in the near future?

First and foremost, we have been able to ascertain that the house has the potential to transform into a multi-functional space, a place where we live, work, carry out research, communicate with the world, into a place of recreation and entertainment, in a public, yet at the same time private area and, therefore, a *total space*, in which everything can be automated and where everything can be perfect: our bodies, objects and furnishings.

In addition we should specify that the total house should represent a new method of intelligent architecture, the features of which can become a space where home automation and electronic and computing device systems interact simultaneously. Unlike a traditional house, the total house becomes a complex *organism*, in which spaces for cognitive experiments are added to private spaces, where individual experiences and those linked to communication can be acquired. We are speaking of an intimate, welcoming environment for every member of the family, equipped with large screens and sophisticated, technological equipment.

The Difference between Domotics or Home Automation and the Smart Home.

Before we tackle the subject of how domotics is considered a tool supported by a principle of aesthetics and design, we need to clarify that the experts currently consider domotics (or home automation)²⁸ to be a system using technologies to control the home via computerised products, which run the energy systems, household appliances and all the devices working within the domestic space. The smart home works on the principle that a house is always connected and has its own life. This principle (Internet of Things) also includes home automation, in other words the use of an Internet connection to achieve a better quality of life, thanks to constantly interconnected devices. Unlike the concept of the smart home, which has developed exponentially all over the world, domotics appears to be difficult to understand, even though it is beginning to become a concrete reality in some countries worldwide, e.g. United States.²⁹

The Total House, the Smart Home and Self-Sufficiency

As it has a life of its own linked to the smart home and to domotics, the architecture of the total house should be considered first and foremost as a self-sufficient body. If we translate this into terms of space, it means that in addition to the technical rooms containing the control panels for the automated systems, it also contains a space for differentiated waste recycling. This room³⁰ is equipped with machinery and containers to compost organic waste, to collect and compress paper and cardboard³¹ and where a new, domestic appliance can transform plastic into petrol and diesel³². A system of photovoltaic and geothermal plants will be able to optimise the plant engineering of home comforts.

The total house will also consist of communal areas, which will have all the facilities for group perceptive-sensorial experiences and where it will be possible to see places, images, films, works of art and design objects. They will, therefore, be equipped with large screens and automation systems.

A disadvantage of these living conditions could be the reduction in the individual's physical activities. Crossing a particular territory, which used to follow a temporal process as the individual moved from one place to another, would now take place standing immobile within one's own four domestic walls. What would be lacking, would be the perceptive aspects and synaesthetic experiences acquired by physically exploring the different places in the world. To solve the former problem, we should specify that the total house may be equipped with a spa area with a gym, sauna and pools or mini swimming pools with hydromassage, whereas the answer to the latter comes from so-called *augmented reality*³³.

Augmented Reality and Holograms as a Domestic Component

In the words of Azuma, one of the leading researchers in the field of Augmented Reality, it is "a technology that allows computer-generated, virtual imagery information to be overlaid on to a live, direct or indirect, real-world environment in real time"³⁴ Unlike Virtual Reality, in which users experience complete immersion in a virtual environment, AR shows virtual information projected on to a real environment. Augmented reality works as a sort of bridge between what is real and what is virtual, in order to create continuity between the two³⁵. This mode enriches sensorial perception by electronically manipulated information, which would otherwise not be perceived by the five senses. If this is true, we can be anywhere extremely quickly. In augmented reality, as confirmed by scientific studies the individual continues to experience normal physical reality, but uses additional information, which can enable interaction and digital manipulation³⁶. For example with recent research about augmented reality we can user wears glasses and by simply using his voice or an integrated touchpad, he can search on Google or Google maps and roam across the Internet, take a look at social media networks or read the news on-line.³⁷ At the same time, the user can also telephone, read and send SMS, take photos or record videos to share. Technology, which is gradually beginning to change our way of seeing the world.

Another interesting discovery, which enables us to perceive space beyond the home, is simulated reality or the *hologram*. This is a three-dimensional image created by the interference of two laser light beams. We are referring to a theory (the holographic theory which began in the twentieth century, thanks to studies by the famous physicist from London University, David Bohm, whereas the holographic technique was invented in 1947 by Hungarian physicist. D.Gabor. Whereas the theory basically confirms that all matter is none other than a collection of information fields, holography enables persons, objects and spaces, which are part of other places, to be recreated and reconstructed within the domestic four walls³⁸ The principle consists of lighting up an object using a consistent laser beam of light and returning the light field reflected on a plate of sensitive material.

For example a recent research has produced the *HoloLens*³⁹. This is a real, wearable, holographic computer, equipped with movement sensors, microphones and audio surround - or should we say, spatial surround, which enables you to understand where the sound is coming from and has a special, specific video-camera. Put it on and you are catapulted into a reality consisting of holograms, in which to sample unprecedented spatial experiences. You could enter a classroom and find yourself strolling through the universe, or dive into a past as vivid and as colourful as the present. Even the most familiar objects could surprise you and appear in a completely new light(nota). If all this is true The *total house* can transform a place into a true container of perceptive, sensorial experiences, in which ever-changing spaces and furnishings can be built according to our requirements.

The House E Automation System as a Tool of Perception

So far, we have analysed the functional features of the total house compared to the smart home and automation applied to the systems. However, we have also mentioned that the total house is a highly flexible, convertible organism. We should specify that spatial and architectural flexibility is not to be understood as a temporal limitation. We are not referring to temporary or nomadic housing, as this would conflict with the individual's increasingly sedentary condition resulting from the phenomena mentioned previously. On the contrary, we are referring to permanent buildings, the structure, construction and

distribution of which can be easily transformed. All this involves movement as a tool generated by automatic systems linked, as a result, to domotics.

Their purpose is to create a domestic/architectural space, which can be worked, moulded and transformed according to whoever lives there, their tastes, needs and even passions, in order to achieve a perfect symbiosis between technology and design.

The Origins of Domotics in Brief

Its origins can be traced back to different people, including William Penn Powers, a building constructor from Wisconsin, who founded the Power Regulator Company in 1891⁴⁰. This was an industry producing temperature regulators, which embraced automation for the very first time. Powers had a revolutionary idea to create a very simple device containing a liquid, which reacted to changes in temperature, capable of regulating the supply of energy for heating. Then, in 1907, the first hotel equipped with an automatic air conditioning system was built in Chicago, and in the 50s, once again in the United States, the idea of Building Automation appeared and the first multiple control device for all the information from the systems in different buildings was created, called System 320. We should point out that Richard Buckminster Fuller applied the first automated systems to a residential home in his 1931 Dymaxion House project, in which a new, different type of formal house construction was one of the first prototypes of an intelligent house. In 1966, Jim Sutherland, a Westinghouse Corporation engineer, created the Echo4, the Electronic Computing House Operator, using the first domestic, automated device for temperature control and for a few electronic devices. Later, in 1970, a group of engineers from Pico Electronics developed one of today's most popular industrial standards in domotics, which exploits the power line for its transmissions⁴¹. Experiments continued in subsequent years, thanks also to the enormous investments by major industries in the sector, which have led to new developments in modern times. The current domotics market is considered one of the most important for industry, second only to that of safety.

Automation and Movement Concept Applied to Architecture: Domotics Extended to Construction

We should point out that movement in architecture used to be considered an expedient to be used for an exclusively formal analysis, based on a principle which considered movement to be associated with the design of a considerably complex form. To prove this, we have the twentieth century, avant-garde, expressionist or futurist buildings or recent works, such as Peter Eisenman's folder theory, or Frank Gehry or Zaha Hadid's complex buildings. As we have seen, increasingly advanced technological research, together with increasingly lightweight, flexible materials, has enabled the idea of movement to also be extended especially on a more substantial level.

However, recent publications and projects on the subject of the house of the future or on the concept of slow housing⁴² still do not have a radical impact on architectural space, but aim as in tradition, on the concept of movement seen as articulation and complexity of form. We are still talking about fixed projects⁴³. Just see the plans of the slow house of Diller Scofidio+ Renfro to witness what said. They also see the house innovated exclusively on the computer and technological level and not on space and on the architectural body.

In the total house there will be entire architectural parts or elements that will move through space (following a movement such as sliding, rotation, slipping, overturning). Thus, we will see to achieve infinite spatial conditions in a relatively short length of time and in this way the architecture acquires subjectivity and can transform into a body capable of representing continually diverse images, which correspond to continually diverse gestures.

Movement of Architecture as Synaesthetic Communication

The walls, volumes and the architectural elements the move slowly, following the instructions designed by architecture which becomes communication. Changing the space means transforming communication and culture. In the total house, moving house brings new prospects and behaviour. Each place remains unfixed; it need not be identified by its irremovable nature. On the contrary, it can be referred to with the prefix "Trans", to identify its transit. Moving house can confirm the desire not to repeat and not to feel repeated. Thanks to its movement, the total house produces a symmetric assembly of unfamiliar thoughts, of untamed

concepts, of a multi-identity move. It encourages a multiple use of a body reaching out once and for all towards new communication systems.

All this triggers a scenic, illusionary aspect, which the architectural body produces by means of its everyday gestures. Sliding, screen-printed windows, rotating drawn walls, continually moving lights which change the perception of space to create special, optical effects, capable of establishing a bond between the perceiver and the perceived space. "Your body is in the world like the heart of an organism: it continues to keep alive, animate and internally feed the visible performance, to form a system with it. When I walk around my apartment, the different aspects which are revealed could not appear as profiles of one and the same thing, if I did not know that each one represents the apartment seen from this or that angle, if I was unaware of my own movement and body as being identical throughout the phases of this movement," Merleau-Ponty⁴⁴ stated in his book *Phenomenology of Perception* of 1945. According to the author, the body ensures the sight remains visible, in the sense that a person understands the meaning of things in reality via the body's ample process of perception. In the total house, what can be seen are the parts, the elements and the objects, of which it consists? They give a meaning to perceptive reality. Above all, time slows down in the total house. Time takes the upper hand in your mind. It is concerned with the way each one of us gives a value to the flow of events, situations, years according to our personality and life experiences. The total house implies the person reflects before making any movement within the space, just as thought lies behind each movement of the house, moved by the person himself.

The Total House and the Different Functional Types of Homes

The total house can be seen in new spatial and functional types of homes, for exemple such as the semi-duplex, the semi-hyogeuem or the double-sided space.

These are types with functional and morphological characteristics that originate from antonyms, such as: open-closed, inside-outside, visible-invisible, order-chaos, above-below. These contrasting terms (time-honoured subject of philosophical studies) never reach the typical equilibrium of tradition, an aspect which gave the individual emotional security (classicism searched for equilibrium between proportions, between empty and full spaces, etc.). On the contrary, they actually find a reason to exist in the most extreme conflict and contrast, creating new, different tensions, capable of arousing multiple sensations in the individual. Some architects have already been applying automation systems for some time to architectural construction, mainly for residential buildings. One example is the "Sliding House" in Suffolk by dRMM Architects, where the external sleeve slides to reveal the glass structure beneath it, or "The Abode of the Outside" by altro_studio, constructed in central Italy using a system of sliding walls to create a completely closed or completely open volume. Yet another is by Next Office, which built the "Sharifi-Ha House" in Teheran, with a series of volumes containing rooms that revolve to face the outside and increase the volume of the house. Furthermore, popular systems are currently used to transform sliding, rotating or overturning elements in the façade. Many designer objects also have the features mentioned above, such as the cabinet which transforms into a table, produced by Giardini Store, or container walls which slide to transform interior design by project designer Miacola. Not forgetting Côté Maison's project with beds descending from the ceiling and many others.

So all these extremely flexible, transformable systems, which can be easily adapted to suit people's requirements, together with the principles behind sustainability and cutting-edge computer technology, may actually represent the architecture of the near future.

Perhaps after the pandemic, our cities will consist of a group of total houses where cars will transform into perfect chauffeurs, in which materials, such as metamaterials⁴⁵ or 3D graphene⁴⁶ will be able to make us invisible or make us live in transparent structures made of very fine but, at the same time, extremely resistant membranes. Perhaps we will not need to design and construct public places, merely because they will be of no use, whereas the total house, for all the reasons mentioned, already contains all the public and collective spaces. Leand perhaps cities of the future will only have underground department stores with long travelators and service lifts. The goods purchased will be sent directly to our homes via the lifts. Thus the total city without public places and collective spaces will be composed of a set of total houses assembled

together where the only moving elements will be linked to the flows of goods organized by a zero emission electrical connection system.

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³ See V. Cesareo *La distanza sociale Una ricerca nelle aree urbane italiane* Franco Angeli, 2007. pag 11

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⁸ See M. Nanni, *Tra inquietudini e incertezze: cosa cercano i giovani d'oggi?* cit. See also A.R. Emili, *altro studio. From the temporary house to the living unit*, plug_in, 2015.

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²² C. Mazzucchelli, Philosopher, technologist and consultant in communication science, marketing and management of organisations. He is the founder of the editorial project, *SoloTablet*, dedicated to the new technologies and to their effects on people's individual, social and professional lives. See C. Mazzucchelli, *Internet e new Media: un forte bisogno di Utopia per immaginare il futuro*, in "Solotablet.it", 25 sept 2013.

²³ Should we be thinking of an ideal society, where justice for the people and respect for the surrounding environment reigns supreme, or will politics be able to handle the current historic moment and establish directives to align us with the changes in culture, thought and economics we'll come across along the way? Also taking into account that the choices we have to make will no longer involve peripheral, procedural or tactical questions, but rather central, strategic dilemmas.

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The inventors of the process and the machine called *Chrysalis*, which will enable 10 tons of plastic to be transformed each month. "The idea is to encourage people to collect waste before it ends up in the oceans via a closed reactor capable of producing fuel." Thus, the waste-eating machine will transform plastic into petrol and diesel, see S. Galeone, in "inabottle.it", 16 jan. 2019

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with each other without coming into direct contact and without using glasses or an HMD. The term "augmented reality" is ascribed to former Boeing researcher, Tom Caudell in 1990. In 1994, Julie Martin founded the Augmented Reality Theater, whose first production featured ballerinas and acrobats performing in and interacting with a virtual world. Moving on to 2007, Reitmayr introduced an AR system which enabled people to view information on urban buildings taken using a mobile device.

³⁶ Augmented reality is a fairly recent technology and is continually evolving. If we were to attempt to give it a very general definition, we could say it represents an altered reality, in which artificial and virtual information is superimposed on the normal reality perceived by our senses.

³⁷ See <https://tecnologia.libero.it/cose-la-realta-aumentata-1054>. See also I. Lagazio *La realtà aumentata è alla portata di tutti: ecco perché* in <https://www.teknoring.com>

³⁸ Holograms are recorded by exposing an optically sensitive material to light in the interference pattern produced by optical beams. See Encyclopedia of Physical Science and Technology (Third Edition), 2003

³⁹ The operation of Microsoft HoloLens is rather complex, to say the least science fiction: photons hit the lenses formed by layers of blue, green and red glass, until they reach the back of the eyes. The light particles, at this point, crossing the light engine of the device at a given angle, generate the holograms displayed by the user. Holo The project, still in prototype phase, is developed in collaboration with NASA and works autonomously, that is it does not need any connection with a smartphone or other device unveiled at the launch of Windows 10 It is not yet known when this wonder will come on the market, nor what it will cost, but in fact it represents a further demonstration of the potential of augmented reality that, in some ways, merges with virtual reality. See tecnologia.libero.it/ See also "microsoft.com"

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